

LINGVO-DIDACTIC BASIS OF CONTROLLING OF THE COMMUNICATIVE-ORIENTED SPEECH SKILLS

Kurbanova Marguba

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Annotation: *In this article the author of the work also dwells on the concept that there are two types of oral communicative tests in the form of interview and in the form of role playing game in the modern lingvo-didactic testing and the choice of this and that form always depends on purpose, objects and stage of testing and teaching. The notion “an oral communicative test in the form of interview” is carried out from linguistics, methods of teaching foreign languages and physiology point of view in the article. The basic components of foreign communicative competence are indicated in the works of Uzbek and foreign scientists, and the new component parts are added that are actual for a specialist of linguistic institute of higher education.*

Keywords: *linguo-didactic basis, oriented speech skills, foreign communicative competence; role playing game; interviewer; characteristics of effectiveness; rating scales; objects of testing; speech interaction.*

ЛИНГВО-ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНО-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННЫМИ РЕЧЕВЫМИ НАВЫКАМИ

Курбанова Маргуба

Андижанский государственный институт иностранных языков

Аннотация: *В данной статье автор работы также останавливается на концепции о том, что в современном лингводидактическом тестировании существуют два вида устных коммуникативных тестов в форме интервью и в форме ролевой игры и выборе того и другого. Эта форма всегда зависит от цели, объектов и этапа проверки и обучения. В статье с точки зрения лингвистики, методики обучения иностранным языкам и физиологии проводится понятие «устный коммуникативный тест в форме интервью». Указаны основные компоненты иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции в работах узбекских и зарубежных ученых, а также добавлены новые составные части, актуальные для специалиста лингвистического вуза.*

Ключевые слова: *лингводидактическая основа, ориентированные речевые навыки, иноязычная коммуникативная компетенция; ролевая игра; интервьюер; характеристики эффективности; рейтинговые шкалы; объекты тестирования; речевое взаимодействие.*

INTRODUCTION. It has become apparent in recent years that there have been marked changes in the goals of language education programmes (Richards and Rodgers, 1987). Today, language students are considered successful if they can communicate effectively in the target language, whereas two decades ago the accuracy of the language produced was the major criterion contributing to the judgement of a student's success or lack of success. These developments termed as 'proficiency movement' or 'promotion of functional (communicative) ability' have placed the focus in language teaching on fluency and communicative effectiveness. So, development of teaching skills has become increasingly important. Theories of communicative competence imply that teachers must do more than just supply learners with a number of language structures to manipulate. Teachers must demonstrate how language items are used and in what situations they are appropriate. They must show learners that a choice of words is possible, indeed necessary, and will colour the propositional content of what they say. They must teach them, in short, the 'use' of language as well as its 'usage'.(Widdowson,1978: 3)

Communicative competence in foreign language teaching is the ability to learn the language means to carry out communication in various types of speech activity in accordance with the decisive communicative tasks, understand, interpret and produce coherent speech. The methods of teaching the native language communicative competence – the ability and a real willingness to communicate adequately targets areas and situations of communication, a willingness to voice interaction and mutual understanding [3.267p.]. So, teaching methods, the result of which is always the educational products created by students: an idea, a hypothesis, a text work, a picture, an article, a plan of their studies, etc. are called heuristic. The method of empathy means to "feel" a person in the state of another object, "introducing" students into the studied objects of the surrounding world, an attempt to feel and know it from within. For example, get used to the essence of wood, cats, clouds and other educational subjects. At the time of the student, the student asks questions to the object-self, trying to perceive, understand and see the answers at a sensual level. The thoughts, feelings, sensations that are born at the same time are the student's educational product, which can then be expressed in an oral, written, and pictorial form. Example: Teacher: - Imagine yourself that you are "Hurricane". How can you describe yourself, what are your feelings? Name your adjectives, verbs, your favorite season, places you occur, your weather. Student: - I am Hurricane. I am the most terrible of all storms. I am dangerous, violent, strong, cruel, noisy and destructive. I destroy houses, carry away cars and telephone boxes. I occur in the springs, throughout the world, but mostly in the United States, especially in the central states. It occur in the afternoon or in the early evening in a hot day. Large clouds appear in the sky. They become darker and darker. In modern conditions it is naive to believe that a full-fledged communication is possible only on the basis of the ability to operate with linguistic material. For a

successful communication process, it is necessary to have the total amount of knowledge that students receive by studying other subjects of the socio humanitarian cycle of the social and humanitarian cycle. English language is a subject whose content is more or less reflected in the subject of the program on a foreign language. Knowledge of regional studies and language history, obtained by students in foreign language lessons [4.277p.], are applied, in turn, in the lessons of the social and humanitarian cycle. Along with the term competence, the term competence is used. These concepts are differentiated as follows: competence – it is complex knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during the course, and which constitutes a substantial component competence; it is the peculiarity of personality, determining its ability to perform activities on the basis of the generated competence. Communicative competence in foreign language teaching – a combination of knowledge of the language system and its units, their construction and operation in a speech on how to formulate thoughts in the target language and understanding the judgments of others, on the national and cultural peculiarities of the carriers studied language [9.15.], about the specifics of the different types of discourse; it is the ability to learn the language means to carry out communication in various types of speech activity in accordance with the decisive communicative tasks, understand, interpret and produce coherent speech. The methods of teaching the native language communicative competence – the ability and a real willingness to communicate adequately targets areas and situations of communication, a willingness to voice interaction and mutual understanding.

METHODS. Methodology of the work are studying and analysis of linguistic, psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature on the theme of investigation, questionnaire and testing of students. Results: the analysis of the purpose and functions of using oral communicative tests in the form of interview has shown importance of their application in practice. Practical implications will be possible for us to use the results of this work in courses of theory of methodology of teaching foreign languages. Purpose of the research in this field to determine the basic advantages of using oral communicative tests in the form of interview.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Means of control of expressive oral speech are the object of the investigation in this work. There are some peculiarities of speech development and conditions of functioning of oral communication and that is why it is necessary to use different means of control of formation of skills in speaking which in their turn repeat techniques of learning of this type of speech activity if we want to increase validity of control. Question-answer work, conversion and ranking of information, oral presentation, interview, oral report, role play, discussion, problem solving, short-form and extensive narrations, oral commentary are used to check up formation of skills in expressive oral speech (reproductive, productive, dialogic, monological). There are two types of oral communicative tests in the form of interview and in the form of role play in the modern linguo-didactic testing. One can see a test as

any examination in the foreign methodology of teaching foreign languages but a test is considered as a complex of tasks prepared in accordance with definite demands to tests, passed approbation on characteristics of efficiency in the Russian methodology of teaching foreign languages. At present time using of oral communicative tests in the form of interview and in the form of role play is directed to estimation of level of foreign communicative competence formation. Then it is necessary to offer definitions of these means of control and reveal the main distinctions of control of oral speech in an oral communicative test in the form of interview in comparison with role play: - interview is directed from interviewer's side in the more extent (he has an initiative in the conversation) than role play by a teacher; - oral testing on the basis of oral communicative tests in the form of interview is a procedure that is prepared and thought thoroughly; - speech actions of a probationer and a tester are programmed in the more extent, for example, interviewer uses obligatory set of phrases in the process of interview, though a probationer is always free in the choice of language means, presentation his views, estimations and so on; - interviewers' questions are determined beforehand - unprepared oral speech is estimated by riders and marker in oral testing with oral communicative test use; - an oral communicative test in the form of role play is built as a rule on a concrete situation but test tasks in an oral communicative test in the form of interview can be varied in the content and form; - technical means are used necessarily in oral testing on the basis of an oral communicative test in the form of interview for the purpose of its objectivization; - method of estimating of received results distinguishes cardinally; - there is no dependence on partner in oral testing on the basis of an oral communicative test in the form of interview as in an oral communicative test in the form of role play; - test tasks in an oral communicative test in the form of interview are adaptive, as test tasks in an oral communicative test in the form of role play are interconnected; - we can check up more extent of material with the help of an oral communicative test in the form of interview than with the help of an oral communicative test in the form of role play. From our point of view an oral communicative test in the form of role play is a means of control for checking up formation of speech abilities and development speech skills within the limits of given situation of communication in compliance with a theme determining content of speech interaction, and roles of probationers. The main distinctions of oral communicative tests in the form interview and oral communicative tests in the form role play from listed above means of control of expressive oral speech are 1) exclusion of prompting, explanation; 2) rigorous regulation of time; 3) evaluation is realized by riders and a marker with the help of prepared rating scales beforehand; 4) audio and videotape recording of test procedure is realized. An oral communicative test in the form of interview we consider after I.A. Tscaturova as a means of control directing to creation special psychological comfortable conditions for probationers with the purpose of revealing of level formation of foreign communicative competence, with the help of

set of test tasks prepared and passed approbation on characteristics of efficiency beforehand, results of testing are estimated with the help of analytical and whole scales. Foreign communicative competence is considered as capability to use facts of foreign language and speech in different conditions of speech communication, sufficiently to a situation of communication. This day the most perspective model of foreign communicative competence is the model offered by L.F. Brahman. Such a model can be the basis for constructing communicative tests, especially for distinguishing criteria of formation of foreign communicative capability of competence. At the same time this model is in need of perfection. Then essence of its separate components has not been established yet, connection between them is not clear enough and in what way they are integrated in the whole foreign communicative competence. [5. 336p.] But working out procedures of oral testing is not necessary to put off till better times. In addition to listed above models of foreign communicative competence there are models offered by J. Murphy (1978), H.G. Widdowson (1978), S. Savignon (1983), G. Caspar (1983), R. Clifford (1985), T. McNamara (1996) and some others.

The need for the stages will depend on the purpose and type of activity in question. Where the emphasis is on practising role play at an elementary level most of the stages could be useful but with less emphasis on the use of observers and a more active monitoring role of the teacher. Feedback would be confined to the main points so as not to risk discouraging learners. It is important that there is enough time for post-play analysis so that learners can assess their performance and evaluate the activity. discussion might focus on: - their general feelings about the activity, e.g. easy, difficult, went well / not so well, problems, useful, enjoyable, satisfying - their impressions on how well they and others interpreted their roles - the effectiveness of their efforts at communication, i.e. appropriacy, accuracy, fluency, use of communication strategies - the relevance of the activity to their learning goals - how well they co-operated - the teacher's interventions (how often? when? why? how?) Various miscellaneous techniques for introducing and conducting role play may be applied. Some of them are: sharing/exchanging information, use of auxiliary techniques and devices (mime, sound, objects, pictures, realistic documents, information files etc.).

We know that, there is no model of foreign communicative competence that contains a professional component and, consequently, it cannot be considered in the context of teaching a foreign language in nonlinguistic institute of higher education. An oral communicative test in the form of interview is a free dialogue, where one should control the following objects: formation of lexical, grammatical, articulate abilities and development of skills such as: keep rules of speech etiquette, express basic speech functions, to speak expressively, independently, with improvisation, in a normal tempo; to express oneself holistically, logically, coherently, fruitfully, to deliver what one has seen, to understand that has been said by an interlocutor momentary and so on and so forth, all these objects are represented in specially worked

out analytical and whole scales. To cut a long story short we can come to the conclusion that there are two types of oral communicative tests in the form of interview and in the form of role play in the modern linguo-didactic testing and choice of this or that form always depends on purpose, objects of testing and stage of study. An oral communicative test in the form of role play is always more predictable, imitating, less creative in comparison with an oral communicative test in the form of interview as it is built on a concrete situation, its test tasks are interconnected and not adaptive.

As we seen in observation of methodological process the most efficient communicator in a foreign language is not always the person who is best at manipulating its structures. It is often the person who is most skilled at processing the complete situation involving himself! herself and the hearer, taking account of what knowledge is already shared between them (e.g. from the situation or from the preceding conversation), and selecting items which will communicate the message effectively. Foreign language learners need opportunities to develop these skills, by being exposed to situations where the emphasis is on using their available resources for communicating meanings as efficiently and economically as possible. Since these resources are limited, this may often entail sacrificing grammatical accuracy in favour of immediate communicative effectiveness. In the same way as for comprehension, the learner needs to acquire not only a repertoire of linguistic items, but also a repertoire of strategies for using them in concrete situations. This can be accomplished by means of communicative activities.

According to Littlewoods (1992) communicative activities have the following purposes:

- 1) they provide ‘whole-task practice’;
- 2) they improve motivation;
- 3) they allow natural learning;
- 4) they can create context which supports learning.

Concerning the teacher’s role in communicative activeness, it should be noted that, especially in the more creative types of activity, unnecessary intervention on the teacher’s part may prevent the learners from becoming genuinely involved in the activity and thus hinder the development of their communicative skills. The teacher becomes less dominant than before, but no less important.

The challenge for the teacher is to:

- 1) develop techniques that encourage students to communicate but do not exceed their foreign language competence;
- 2) place students in meaningful life situations;
- 3) give the students enough freedom to experiment with the language;
- 4) create a supportive classroom environment in which the student feels free to communicate.

RESULTS. In the same way as for comprehension, the learner needs to acquire not only a repertoire of linguistic items, but also a repertoire of strategies for using them in concrete situations. This can be accomplished by means of communicative activities. According to Littlewoods (1992) communicative activities have the following purposes: • they provide ‘whole-task practice’; • they improve motivation; • they allow natural learning; • they can create context which supports learning. Concerning the teacher’s role in communicative activities, it should be noted that, especially in the more creative types of activity, unnecessary intervention on the teacher’s part may prevent the learners from becoming genuinely involved in the activity and thus hinder the development of their communicative skills. The teacher becomes less dominant than before, but no less important. The challenge for the teacher is to: • develop techniques that encourage students to communicate but do not exceed their foreign language competence; • place students in meaningful life situations; • give the students enough freedom to experiment with the language; • create a supportive classroom environment in which the student feels free to communicate. 84 There are also communicative activities in which the teacher can take part as a ‘co-communicator’ . Provided the teacher can maintain this role without becoming dominant, it enables him/her to give guidance and stimuli from ‘inside the activity’ (Littlewood, 1992: 19).

Speaking skills enable learners to enter the community of the target language communicators speaking skills are not uniform in their structure. They comprise cognitive, linguistic and phonetic skills. In order to realise communicative intentions speakers/ learners should possess relevant communicative competences which lead to communicative ability. The development of communicative ability requires a range of suitable classroom activities. These activities should contain communicative urgency, i.e., the learners should experience necessity to say something and a need and reason to communicate with their partners. Thus, learners may be motivated to communicate by the enjoyment of playing a game, by the challenge and satisfaction in solving a problem or presenting an academic speech in the target language.

In order to feel confident enough to contribute freely to a discussion, the learners must be familiar with the conventions of this type of discourse and with ways of intervening, commenting, seeking clarification, expressing an opinion, agreeing, disagreeing, referring back, emphasising, expanding, etc. in the target language. To maximise learner participation it is helpful to structure their contributions in the early stages and to devise ways of encouraging everyone to contribute. Kramsch (1984) suggests giving learners cards with discourse cues and ways of expressing them in order to ensure that the discussion is not unduly directed by the teacher or dominated by a handful of learners.

Some discussion activities may be practised before the real discussion takes place to help the learners feel more confident:

- 1) practice in expressing statements (expressing agreement/disagreement and explaining);
- 2) practice in ranking people, objects, concepts according to criteria supplied or practice in ranking ideas relating to a story;
- 3) practice in decision making or solving a moral dilemma. Activities which require learners to narrate are a welcome break from the 'Ping-Pong' exchanges of interviews and discussions, provide valuable practice in developing fluency and stimulate learners' creativity.

In real life, everyone narrates: telling others about something that happened, talking about a good book or film, telling a story, anecdote, joke, etc.

Narrative activities: - provide opportunities for learners to engage in extended discourse in contrast to the brief exchanges of most other speaking activities; - develop fluency;

- provide practice in listening with concentration;
- stimulate learners' imagination; - activate a wide range of vocabulary in context; - require little advance preparation and can readily be integrated with textbook material.

Reconstituting a story, imagining the end of an unfinished story or creating narratives from pictures, objects and words are interesting and satisfying activities and help learners to develop skills which can be applied to other kinds of interaction. Discussion of the learners' future academic research themes can be mentioned as one of possible interactions on a higher level leading to the academic speech at the presentation of the learners' Bachelor papers. Project work can be used as link bridging the gap between a free social interaction and an academically or professionally meaningful presentation. Project work offers learners a series of meaningful and relevant activities which lead to their assuming responsibility for their own learning both as a social group and as individuals. It is a particularly natural way of integrating skills as learners study, discuss, take notes, write reports and present results orally and in writing. An important result of the project IS (independent study skills) the increased motivation, selfconfidence and autonomy of learners.

CONCLUSION. Thus, communication skills form a dichotomous opposition, organizing science system of language: communication skills addressee opposed communicative skills of the author. Said opposition is neutralized in the language of the person, in some speech situations serving as the addressee, in others - its manufacturer. Therefore, the effectiveness of speech activity of a native speaker is directly dependent on the quality of formation as an intro-subjective and extra-subjective communicative abilities, as the communicative abilities of the recipient, and communicative skills of the author. As a kind of synthesis of substantive content of the term communicative competence perceived definition of belonging M.R. Lvov. In the dictionary-reference book on methods of teaching the English language, he writes:

Communicative competence – a term denoting the knowledge of the language (native and non-native), its phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, style, speech culture, possession of these means of language and speech mechanisms – speaking, listening, reading and writing – in the range of social, professional and cultural needs of the person [6.26p.]. One of the most important characteristics of the language is personality. It is acquired as a result of natural speech and as a result of special education.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Azimov Ae.G., Zshukin A.N. Dictionary of methodical terms (theory and practice of teaching languages). Saint-Petersburg: “Zlatoust”, 1999. 472 p.
2. Antonova, E.S. Methodology for teaching the Russian language: communicative-activity approach: textbook / Antonova, E.S. – M.: KNORUS, 2007. – 460 c.
3. Baluyan S.R. Testing of foreign competence in oral speech of schoolleavers in the speciality linguistics and cross-cultural communication (on the material of English). Taganrog: abstract of dissertation of candidate of pedagogical science, 1999. 267 p.
4. Grom E.N. Content and forms of control of achieved level of foreign communicative competence of schoolchildren from 10-11 forms in the schools with profound studying foreign language. M.: Dissertation of candidate of pedagogical science, 1999. 277 p.
5. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. Theory of teaching foreign languages. Linguodidactics and methodology: textbook-manual for university students / Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. – 3rd edition. – M.: Publishing Center “Academy”, 2006. –336 c.
6. Morozova A.L. Pedagogical basis for the development of foreign language communicative competence of students of non-language faculties of pedagogical high school (Unpublished candidate dissertation). Tomsk State University, Tomsk, Russian Federation, 2010. -26 p.
7. Peshnya I.S. Interactive learning technologies as tools of the professional competence of the student paramilitary institution. Irkutsk, 2010. -11 p.
8. Yuldashev Z.Kh., Ashurova D.N. Innovative-didactic program complex and new formalized model of education. Malaysian Journal of Mathematical Sciences 6 (1):, P.: 97-103. (2012).
9. Porter, P. A. (1986). How Learners Talk to Each Other: Input and Interaction in Task-centered Discussion. In Day, R. (Ed.), Talking to Learn: Conversation in second Language Acquisition. Rowley, Mass.: Newbury House.
10. Postovsky, V. (1970). Effects of Delay in Oral Practice at the Beginning of Second Language Learning. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, University of California, Berkeley.